

Developing Review Comprehension in Dual Education: Problems and Solutions

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Abstract:

New pedagogical technologies used in the educational process serve to develop skills and competencies necessary for life. The effectiveness of the dual education system is being confirmed. In fact, education should be an integral part of real life, teaching processes should prepare the learner for all aspects of life and professional activity. Each academic subject serves to form one common competence. A person learns and assimilates existence through the sense organs, but understanding related to perception is not studied separately as a skill and qualification, nor does it exist as a competence in the system of training a well-rounded person in didactics. After all, a person goes through the processes of viewing and understanding before reading and understanding in the course of listening. In the article, reading comprehension is researched as an important pedagogical factor, not a simple physiological phenomenon, and its description is given at the level of skill, skill and competence. It is based on the fact that observation is a necessary tool for forming analytical thinking.

Keywords: review, skill, skill, competence, perception, analytical thinking, listening comprehension, speaking, observation, look, compare, estimate, educational tasks, question, didactics, methodology, generality, specificity, essence, phenomenon, pragmatic approach, assessment.

Enter. In the world experience, different approaches are used to prepare students for the profession. Among them, it is becoming increasingly popular that a dual approach is more effective. As Adam

Smith stated in his well-known work: "In dual education - in the workplace, the master should be considered to teach the apprentice the traditional methods of the trade, because working with the master will increase the interest of the young workers in the profession . " ¹The system of dual education of a scientist, the practice of the European education system, shows that it is the product of interaction between educational organizations and employers for the successful professional and social adjustment of the future specialist. The student is involved in the production process as an employee of the enterprise at the initial stages of the educational process. In his famous "Inquiries into the Nature and Causes of the Wealth of Nations" (1776), Adam Smith argued that apprenticeship and mentoring systems in dual education should be considered traditional methods of vocational training in the workplace, because working under a master, young workers learned the basics of education. the vocational training model involves the involvement of enterprises in the process of personnel training, which leads to very high costs associated with the training of employees, because they know very well that the costs of high-quality vocational training are a reliable investment of capital. At the same time, he states that they are interested not only in the results of education, but also in the content of education and its organization ².

The dual education system is an activity of seeing and understanding theory in practice. **Reading comprehension** is not isolated as a skill or a skill. Part of it is assessed as part of reading comprehension skills in language education. It mainly focuses on understanding pictures, videos and audiovisual materials. In international pedagogy, visual understanding (*understanding vision*) does not exist as a separate competence. People with high visual perception skills have the ability to recognize and analyze visual elements, identify patterns and relationships, as well as obtain information and draw conclusions. according to the information provided. This competence is especially important in fields such as design, media, marketing, advertising and art.

Research methodology. Review and understanding competence is the activity of the learner to review and understand the situation, subject, process, analyze and express his own conclusion. This means not only pictures and video materials, but the whole subject, situation, process and activity that the student will face in the future life. Also, in the dual education system aimed at preparing the requirements for the profession, it will be possible to evaluate their skills and qualifications based on studying the production processes along with the lessons. The development of the mechanism of transformation of the skill of understanding into skills and competence is one of the important pedagogical and methodical problems that must be solved today.

F.I.Buslaev writes: "the first and most important thing is to develop the practical ability to understand what is expressed by speech forms and to use them correctly, that is, as the educated people say, through oral and written exercises, the student can easily learn speech forms typical of conversation and writing. we form the skill of understanding ³. "It is neither possible nor necessary to teach a high school student all the linguistic knowledge accumulated by mankind over the centuries. Therefore, choosing the most necessary knowledge from the mother tongue is one of the main issues.

The main criterion for choosing knowledge from the mother tongue is its level of usefulness and practical application. We understand useful knowledge from the mother tongue as knowledge that serves to form the skills of children's literate writing, creative thinking, correct and fluent

1Smith A. "Investigation of the nature and causes of the wealth of nations". - M.: EXMO, 2007. - Series: anthology of economic media - 960s).

2Sudakova, L. V. dual education of the model essence and main features / L. V. Sedakova. - Text : direct // education and education — 2016. — No. 2 (7). - PP. 62-64. -

3 Buslaev F.I About teaching the domestic language. 2nd ed. M., 1867. (trans .: L., 1941).

expression of the product of thought in oral and written forms in accordance with the conditions of speech, and ensures their upbringing and development in the spirit of high human qualities.⁴

In the first years of independence, systematic studies were conducted on the selection of educational materials, which are the basis for the creation of educational tasks, and the determination of the purpose and content of mother tongue education.

Sh.Yusupova's doctoral thesis⁵ conducts research on the scientific-methodical basis of the development of students' thinking in the current Uzbek literary language classes, while developing the scientific-methodical basis of the development of students' thinking in mother tongue education, he also pays special attention to educational tasks that develop thinking.

Kh. Muhiddinova has done important work in systematizing the education of the Uzbek language as a state language, ensuring coherence and continuity. In particular, it has been improving educational tasks based on the principle of continuity for the continuous education system.⁶

K. Husanbaeva's inclusion of the teacher in the content of education⁷ is an extremely correct approach. Because in the teaching of the mother tongue, especially in controlling the exercises in the classroom, it is very important for the teacher to set an example directly in the development of students' literary pronunciation skills in the necessary places. In addition, the independent thinking and problem-based teaching approaches developed by the scientist for literary education will help in the correct formation of teaching assignments in the teaching of the mother tongue.

Australian scientist Jack Richards was specially engaged⁸ in methodical, psychological-pedagogical research of educational tasks in the field of international pedagogy, especially language didactics. It should be noted that in its time, Western pedagogy focused on practicality. The first pragmatic ideas were the American philosopher and pedagogue D. Developed by Dewey.⁹

In fact, mother tongue, national words are the basis of intellectual development and understanding of the world. It is very important to take care of the timely development of the student's speech, to pay attention to his literacy. The more rich and logical a student's speech is, the easier it is for him to express his thoughts, the wider his ability to understand the world and existence, the more students can engage in meaningful and full-fledged communication with peers or adults in various speech situations, and the more active their thinking is in development.

Analysis and results (Analysis and results). All of this depends on correctly guiding the student through educational tasks, asking the right questions, and giving meaningful and logical answers. The student receives initial information about the surrounding world and human activities through the native language used at home, in the classroom and on the street. Therefore, the first task of the school is to teach children to speak fluently and logically in their mother tongue. The better students can speak in their native language, the more vividly, beautifully and meaningfully they can express their thoughts in oral and written form.

4 Zhulomov A., Ne'matov G. Ona Language Education mazmuni . Keepers to use the methodology . – T.: The shepherd . 1996. 9th.

5 Yusupova Sh.J. Scientific-methodological foundations of developing students' thinking in modern Uzbek literary language classes: Ped. doctor of science... diss. - Tashkent: TDPI, 2005. - 270 p.

6 Muhiddinova Kh. Improvement of the scientific-methodical foundations of ensuring the continuity of Uzbek language teaching at the educational stages . science. nom-di diss. TDPI -Tashkent, 2011. -270 p

7Gusanboeva K. Scientific and methodical associations of literary education in the field of independent thought: ped. fan. doc diss. author's abstract. -T.: TDPU, 2006. - 262 p.

8<https://www.professorjackrichards.com/mother-tongue-teaching-vs-foreign-language-teaching/>

9 John Dewey. Society and its problems John Dewey . The Public and its Problems . Denver , 1927. / J. Dewey. Society and its problems. — Translation from English: I. I. Murberg , A. B. Tolstov, E. N. Kosilova. - M., 2002.

Therefore, the most important issue today is to bring mother tongue education closer to life, to strengthen its practical importance. The linguistic landscape of the world and national cultures are formed in the student's thinking through the mother tongue. If the mother tongue is taught as a value and not as a mere subject, students will develop self-reflection and national pride. Then students will be more interested in learning their mother tongue. Students should learn the national mentality, life, and cultural heritage of the nation through the mother tongue. Of course, this is done through the development of educational tasks of a pragmatic nature. In mother tongue classes, students learn the rules of the language based on questions and assignments. The sentences and texts given in the exercise serve to increase the student's vocabulary, but how to work on them remains a problem. Mother tongue classes not only teach **comprehension, comprehension, speaking**, writing essays, but also make sure that the mother tongue is a living and natural language if the comprehension is directed to educational literature through assignments.

Summary and suggestions (Conclusion/Recommend.) *Reading comprehension* can also serve as the basis of education, as well as listening comprehension, reading comprehension, speaking and writing skills, because in school education, students do not acquire these skills, they acquire them as part of reading comprehension skills during the lesson. But in mother tongue education, there is also the problem of developing analytical thinking in determining the speaking skills that students should acquire today. Today, speaking requirements for teaching a foreign language are applied even in the mother tongue, but it does not give the expected effect, in our opinion. As a carrier of the language, the student who can hear and understand, can read, speak, and write can understand the message and information he has just heard (audio, video song, poem, ghazal, question); understand the content of the read text; on the basis of the received information, it is necessary to set requirements to speak fluently in literary language, and to write down one's attitude meaningfully (essay). Educational tasks, which are one of the smallest elements of the methodology, are one of the important levers that lead mother tongue education to the right path.

However, in **dual education**, the issue of improving learning tasks that develop the ability to directly **look at and understand** has not been studied as a separate research object. Our analysis shows that reforms in mother tongue education depend to a large extent on how the educational tasks are set. Comprehension of educational tasks (analytical thinking) aimed at developing comprehension, comprehension, speaking and essay skills, directing the questions that will make the student think, clarify his mind, and develop his worldview will lead the mother tongue education in the direction we want.

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